

Enhanced Faster R-CNN for Industrial PCB Defect Detection Toward Robotic Visual Inspection

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Abstract— Reliable printed circuit board (PCB) defect detection is essential for quality inspection in electronics manufacturing, where structural faults may affect circuit reliability and production yield. In this paper, an evaluation of an improved Faster R-CNN framework for PCB defect detection for robotic visual inspection is presented. The model is evaluated on a PCB-Defect-Detection dataset which includes categories including missing hole, mouse bite, open circuit, short, spur and spurious copper. By integrating stronger feature representation, dataset-adaptive proposal generation, and refined region-level detection, the framework achieves detection performance under fine-grained PCB defect conditions. Results achieve 91.21% precision, 98.06% recall, 94.51% F1-score, and 96.60% mAP@0.50, indicating its potential for industrial visual inspection. The reported detection performance, together with a 47.26 FPS inference rate, supports the framework’s potential for robotic PCB quality inspection.

Keywords—PCB defect detection, Faster R-CNN, object detection, robotic inspection.

I. Introduction

In the electronics industry, automated printed circuit board (PCB) defect detection plays an important role in ensuring circuit reliability and manufacturing quality, as even minor structural faults can affect production yield and device performance. However, accurate PCB defect detection remains challenging because defects are often small, visually similar, and located within complex copper patterns.

Deep object detection frameworks have been increasingly adopted for visual inspection tasks due to their ability to learn discriminative features and localize defect regions. Two-stage detectors such as Faster R-CNN [1] are particularly suitable for fine-grained localization, while deep residual backbones can improve feature representation through deeper hierarchical learning [2]. In contrast, one-stage detectors such as RetinaNet provide efficient dense detection but may require careful handling of class imbalance and small object localization [3].

In this paper, an improved Faster R-CNN framework is evaluated for fine-grained PCB defect detection toward robotic visual inspection. The framework integrates ResNet-101 with CBAM-based feature refinement [4], K-Means-based anchor optimization, and a refined RoI detection head to improve feature discrimination, proposal quality, and region-level classification.

II. Related Work

PCB defect detection has been widely studied for automated optical inspection and industrial quality control. Earlier works introduced PCB datasets and deep learning pipelines for evaluating common defects such as missing hole, mouse bite, open circuit, short, spur, and spurious copper [5, 6]. Deep object detectors further improved inspection by learning defect-specific visual features beyond handcrafted image processing rules.

Faster R-CNN-based methods have been explored for small PCB defect localization because two-stage detectors provide strong region proposal and localization capability [1, 7]. Recent PCB inspection studies compared Faster R-CNN, RetinaNet,

and YOLO-based detectors to examine the trade-off between detection accuracy and efficiency. Lightweight one-stage detectors and PCBA inspection models have also been studied for faster deployment in manufacturing environments [9, 10].

Despite these advances, the combined effect of attention-guided feature refinement, dataset-adaptive anchor optimization, and region-level two-stage detection remains less explicitly analyzed for robotic PCB visual inspection. To address this gap, this study evaluates an enhanced Faster R-CNN framework integrating ResNet-101 with CBAM, K-Means-based anchor optimization, and a refined RoI detection head for fine-grained PCB defect detection.

III. Methodology

The overall workflow of the proposed PCB defect detection framework is illustrated in Figure 1. The framework follows a structured pipeline consisting of dataset preparation, feature extraction, region proposal generation, RoI-based classification, and deployment-oriented evaluation. This design allows the model to address fine-grained PCB defect localization while maintaining a practical balance between detection accuracy and inspection speed.

Figure 1. Workflow of the proposed PCB defect detection framework.

A. Dataset and Preprocessing

The PCB-Defect-Detection dataset from Roboflow Universe was used as the evaluation benchmark [8]. The dataset contains

3,079 images from six defect categories: short, spur, missing hole, mouse bite, open circuit, and spurious copper. These categories represent common structural defects found in printed circuit boards and are suitable for evaluating fine-grained industrial defect detection. The images were resized and normalized before object detection-based evaluation to ensure consistent input dimensions and stable feature learning. The dataset was divided into training, validation, and testing subsets so that model optimization and final evaluation could be conducted under a consistent experimental protocol.

B. Enhanced Detection Framework

An enhanced Faster R-CNN framework [1] was evaluated for fine-grained PCB defect detection. The model uses ResNet-101 as the backbone network to extract deep hierarchical features from PCB images [2]. To strengthen feature representation, the CBAM module was integrated after the final ResNet-101 feature stage before region proposal generation, allowing channel-wise and spatial attention to refine defect-relevant responses without applying attention after every residual block [4]. This design helps improve feature discrimination for small and visually similar PCB defects while controlling additional computational cost. K-Means-based anchor optimization was applied to adapt the anchor boxes to the bounding-box distribution of the PCB defect dataset. This dataset-adaptive proposal strategy helps the region proposal network generate more suitable candidate regions for small-scale defects. The refined RoI detection head then performs region-level classification and bounding-box regression to improve localization accuracy and class discrimination. By combining CBAM-based feature refinement, optimized anchors, and a two-stage detection structure, the framework is designed to improve both proposal quality and final defect recognition.

C. Evaluation and Deployment Analysis

The proposed model was evaluated using precision, recall, F1-score, mean IoU, mAP, and mAR to measure both classification and localization performance. Precision measures the correctness of detected defects, while recall reflects the ability of the model to reduce missed defects, which is particularly important in industrial quality inspection. The F1-score provides a balanced measurement of precision and recall, and mAP@0.50 was used to evaluate detection performance under an IoU threshold of 0.50. To address the robotic visual inspection objective, deployment-oriented metrics were also reported, including average inference time, inference speed, and model size. These metrics provide a practical indication of whether the enhanced detector can support inspection scenarios where both detection reliability and processing speed are important.

IV. Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents the quantitative comparison of the proposed enhanced Faster R-CNN framework with RetinaNet and YOLOv11n on the PCB-Defect-Detection dataset. The proposed model achieved 91.21% precision, 98.06% recall, 94.51% F1-score, and 96.60% mAP@0.50. Although RetinaNet obtained a slightly higher precision, the proposed model produced sub-

stantially higher recall, F1-score, and mAP@0.50, indicating a stronger overall detection balance for fine-grained PCB defect inspection. The high recall is particularly important in industrial quality control because missed defects may lead to defective circuit boards passing through the inspection pipeline.

Table 1. Comparative performance on the PCB-Defect-Detection dataset

Model	Precision	Recall	F1-score	mAP@0.50
RetinaNet	91.67%	90.06%	90.86%	83.76%
YOLOv11n	87.85%	86.09%	86.96%	90.60%
Proposed Model	91.21%	98.06%	94.51%	96.60%

The deployment-oriented results are reported in Table 2. The proposed model achieved an inference speed of 47.26 FPS with an average inference time of 21.16 ms/image on a CUDA-enabled GPU. These results provide practical evidence for the robotic visual inspection objective of this study, showing that the enhanced detector maintains strong detection accuracy while achieving real-time-level processing speed. The model size of 219.02 MB also indicates that the framework is more suitable for GPU-supported industrial inspection systems than for highly constrained embedded devices.

Table 2. Deployment performance of the proposed model

Deployment Metric	Value
Execution device	CUDA-enabled GPU
Average inference time	21.16 ms/image
Inference speed	47.26 FPS
Model size	219.02 MB

Figure 2 presents the normalized confusion matrix of the proposed model. The dominant diagonal responses indicate reliable class-wise recognition across PCB defect categories, supporting the high recall and mAP@0.50 reported in Table 1. This result further confirms that the proposed framework can distinguish fine-grained defect types with strong class-level consistency.

Figure 2. Normalized confusion matrix of the proposed model on PCB defect categories.

Figure 3 shows qualitative detection examples produced by the proposed model. The visual results demonstrate that the frame-

work can localize small PCB defects and assign defect labels under complex copper-pattern backgrounds. Together, the quantitative, deployment, confusion-matrix, and qualitative results demonstrate the effectiveness of combining CBAM-based feature refinement, K-Means-based anchor optimization, and a two-stage detection framework for robotic PCB visual inspection.

Figure 3. Qualitative PCB defect detection results of the proposed model.

V. Conclusion

This paper presented an enhanced Faster R-CNN framework for fine-grained PCB defect detection toward robotic visual inspection. The proposed framework integrates ResNet-101-based feature extraction, CBAM-guided feature refinement, K-Means-based anchor optimization, and a refined RoI detection head to improve defect localization and classification under complex PCB patterns. By focusing on small and visually similar defect categories, the study addresses an important challenge in automated industrial quality inspection.

The experimental results demonstrate that the proposed model provides a strong overall detection balance compared with RetinaNet and YOLOv11n. The framework achieved 91.21% precision, 98.06% recall, 94.51% F1-score, and 96.60% mAP@0.50, showing its effectiveness for reliable PCB defect detection. The high recall is particularly important for industrial inspection, where missed defects can lead to serious reliability issues in electronic manufacturing. The normalized confusion matrix and qualitative detection results further support the model's ability to distinguish fine-grained PCB defect categories with consistent class-wise recognition.

In addition to detection accuracy, the deployment-oriented evaluation shows that the proposed model achieved 47.26 FPS with an average inference time of 21.16 ms/image on a CUDA-enabled

GPU. These results indicate that the framework has practical potential for GPU-supported robotic PCB quality inspection systems. Future work may extend this study by evaluating the model on larger industrial datasets, testing its robustness under real production-line conditions, and optimizing the architecture for lightweight real-time deployment on embedded inspection platforms.

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